

THE TECHNOLOGY OF USING GAMES AND TOYS IN THE PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AND CREATING A MODERN MEDIA ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the technology of using games and toys in the psychological development of preschool children and the creation of a modern media environment.*

Keywords: psychological development, toys, game technologies, media environment, interactive tools.

Introduction

Games and toys are among the primary tools for the psychological development of preschool children. These tools help shape children's cognitive, social, and emotional abilities. The modern media environment has introduced new technologies into this process, including interactive games and electronic devices. This article examines the role of game and toy utilization technologies, as well as the modern media environment, in the development of children.

Main Part

If the creative abilities of children in preschool educational institutions are developed through innovative games and toys, the new generation of the 21st century will grow into mentally and spiritually mature individuals. They will assimilate their surroundings based on critical and analytical perspectives, broaden their understanding of the world, acquire intellectually advanced knowledge, and develop independent thinking and problem-solving skills. As a result, by the age of 7, children will be well-prepared to enter the general education school system.

The preschool period is a phase of intensive psychological development, which is carried out based on the conditions formed in early childhood. Innovations emerge in various aspects of psychological development, characterized by new qualities and structural features. This process occurs due to several factors, including communication with adults and peers, acquiring knowledge through different forms and types of activities (such as play, creativity, and daily life). Alongside these innovations, complex social-psychological forms develop, which constitute the individual and its structural elements (such as character, interests, and more) through the development of psychophysiological functions. These include communication, cognition, and activity as well as their core components—abilities and interests. At the same time, the personal organization and socialization of the child continue to develop, which is most evident at the psychophysiological level, in cognitive functions, and in psychomotor skills. New psychological functions, or higher levels, are formed, characterized by features that enable children to adapt to social conditions and the demands of life. The preschool age typically spans from 3 to 6-7 years. During this time, the child begins to separate from adults, leading to changes in the social situation. The child steps beyond the boundaries of the family for the first time and enters the adult world, which operates with specific laws and rules. The scope of communication expands: preschool children begin visiting shops, clinics, and interacting with peers—experiences that are crucial for their development.

It is worth noting that the leading type of activity during the preschool years is various forms of play. Specifically, in the 21st century, innovative toys play a significant role in raising a generation heavily reliant on gadgets and smartphones into well-rounded individuals. Intellectual games and modern toys are activity forms used by preschool children to replicate certain aspects of human activity and master the forms of relationships they will practice later. Children achieve this by substituting one object for another, simplifying real actions. At this age, plot-based role-playing games develop particularly well. These games are centered on the role chosen by the child and the actions required to implement that role.

Results

Game Technologies in Children's Psychological Development:

1. Developmental Toys and Activities:

- **Constructive Games:** Building and assembling toys (e.g., LEGO, blocks) enhance children's logical thinking.
- **Role-Playing Games:** Help children understand social roles in society (e.g., roles of doctor, teacher, chef).
- **Emotion-Enhancing Games:** Activities such as playing with kinetic sand or watercolor painting reduce stress and foster imagination.

2. Interactive Technologies:

- Modern gaming technologies improve children's focus and problem-solving skills.
- Virtual reality provides opportunities for children to explore new knowledge visually and kinesthetically.
- Educational processes are organized through games using e-books and multimedia tools.

The Impact of Modern Media Environments on Children's Development:

• Positive Effects:

1. **Accessibility to Information:** Modern technologies provide children with access to a wide range of knowledge.
 2. **Development of Creativity:** Digital technologies expand children's worldview and foster creativity.
 3. **Harmony of Play and Learning:** Interactive platforms offer educational and developmental games.
- **Negative Effects:**
 1. **Reduced Interpersonal Communication:** Excessive time spent with digital devices may decrease social skills.
 2. **Difficulty in Maintaining Attention:** Rapid visual and audio stimuli may make it harder for children to concentrate.
 3. **Reduced Physical Activity:** Overdependence on media environments negatively affects children's physical development.

Recommendations for Integrating Game Technologies and Media Environments:

1. **Balancing Games and Technologies:** Promote the use of developmental toys alongside electronic devices.
2. **Managing Children's Time:** Set limits on screen time to ensure attention is also given to traditional games.
3. **Educational Programs for Parents and Teachers:** Organize training on selecting appropriate media environments and games for children.
4. **Development of Interactive Toys:** Design toys that encourage activity and stimulate creative thinking in children.

Conclusion

The harmony between games, toys, and the modern media environment plays a crucial role in the psychological development of preschool children. Leveraging technologies effectively is essential for fostering children's growth and ensuring their holistic development.

The Impact of Innovative Toys Includes:

Intellectual Development:

• Logic and Problem-Solving:

Modern toys, such as construction sets, puzzles, and logic games, enhance children's logical thinking, problem-solving, and ability to find creative solutions.

• Language and Speech Development:

Interactive toys, musical toys, and storybooks help expand children's vocabulary, improve their speech, and develop listening skills.

• Memory and Concentration:

Through toys, children learn to remember rules, colors, shapes, and numbers, thereby improving their memory and ability to concentrate.

Social Development:

• Collaboration and Communication:

Toys designed for group play teach children how to collaborate, communicate, and develop interpersonal relationships.

• Social Behavior:

Through toys, children learn about social interactions, rules of play, and how to treat others with respect.

Physical Development:

• Motor Skills:

Moving toys and sports equipment improve children's fine and gross motor skills, help them maintain balance, and enhance coordination.

• Healthy Lifestyle:

Sports toys and outdoor play equipment encourage physical activity and foster the development of a healthy lifestyle.

The proper use, time management, and adaptation of pedagogical approaches to meet modern needs are essential.

The impact of recommended innovative toys for preschool children in fostering a well-rounded generation is significant. These toys positively influence children's intellectual, social, physical, and emotional development.

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MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING PSIXOLOGIK RIVOJLANISHIDA O‘YIN VA O‘YINCHOQLARDAN FOYDALANISH TEXNOLOGIYASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning psixologik rivojlanishi va zamonaviy media muhitini yaratishda o'yinlar va o'yinchoqlardan foydalanish texnologiyasi tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: psixologik rivojlanish, oʻyinchoqlar, oʻyin texnologiyalari, media muhiti, interaktiv vositalar.